

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report providing a listing of sub-grid scale processes related to turbulent mixing and cloud microphysics that are not realistically represented, and require further improvement.

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WP4

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1 Executive summary

In climate models processes that occur on scales smaller than model resolution are accounted for using so-called parameterizations. The type of parameterization used can have a large effect on model results. As the resolution of models is increased, some processes are resolved on a model grid and no longer need to be parameterized. The others, operating at smaller scales, will still need to be parameterized even in future, high-resolution models.

In the second phase of the project, we recommend to address and improve two sub-grid schemes:

1. turbulent mixing scheme, with particular focus on vertical mixing in stable stratification,
2. microphysics scheme, with particular focus on partitioning of hydrometeors (cloud water, rain, snow, ice and graupel).

Work described in this report shows that there is significant uncertainty associated with the choice of turbulence and microphysics parameterization. We observed high sensitivity of the amount of low-level clouds over the ocean to the type of turbulence parameterization. The Smagorinsky parameterization is beneficial in that it adapts to the model resolution, but it is found to give too little vertical mixing in regions with strong temperature inversion. In microphysics parameterizations, condensed and frozen water is arbitrarily divided into categories, which leads to discrepancies between models, e.g. in the amount of ice in clouds. We started to explore alternative sub-grid schemes that could potentially replace parameterizations used today.

2 Conclusion & Results

Parameterization of sub-grid scale (SGS) turbulence has large impact on low-level clouds over the ocean. In IFS-FESOM turbulence in the mixed layer is modeled with the eddy diffusivity mass flux (EDMF) scheme, and a shallow convection parameterization is used. This approach gives good agreement with observations in the trade-wind regime, as we show by comparing profiles of Cycle 2 simulations with soundings from the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO).

In most of the nextGEMS ICON simulations, turbulence is modeled using the Smagorinsky scheme and there is no parameterization of shallow convection. The Smagorinsky model is typically used in large-eddy simulations (LES). The rationale for its use in global ICON simulations is that it adapts to changes in resolution, it has fewer tuning parameters and the future ESM resolution will be comparable to that of coarse LES. However, comparison with observations over subtropical oceans suggests that this approach provides too little vertical mixing in the case of stable stratification. On the other hand, comparison with observations over the Southern Ocean suggests the simulated mixing is too strong in the conditions of extremely stable stratification over the surface. This effect is related to stability correction function in combination with vertical resolution of the model grid. In consequence, liquid water path (LWP) in stratocumulus and cumulus regions is around two times larger in ICON than in IFS-FESOM, as we show based on Cycle 3 simulations. Moreover, the occurrence of low-level clouds over the Southern Ocean is underestimated while the mixed-layer depth overestimated with respect to observations.

An attempt to fix this issue was one of the Cycle 3 ICON simulations that used a Smagorinsky scheme with a modified stability correction function in order to increase the amount of vertical

mixing in regions with high stability. This modification was successful in decreasing the amount of stratocumuli, but failed in decreasing the amount of cumuli. In consequence, the amount of liquid water no longer linearly depended on the lower tropospheric stability, as it is expected based on long-term observations. It shows that low-level clouds are in fact strongly dependent on the SGS turbulence model and that a more physically-based modification of the Smagorinsky scheme is required.

Another parameterization that contributes to model uncertainty is cloud microphysics. Both ICON and IFS-FESOM use single-moment bulk microphysics, but with different details. In particular, ICON simulates snow, ice and graupel while IFS-FESOM only snow and ice. In consequence, in ICON 15 % and 20 % of frozen water is considered ice and graupel, respectively, while in IFS-FESOM 35 % is ice. Since graupel and ice sediment with very different velocities, this can affect the lifetime of clouds.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP4**Relevance in this deliverable?**

To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5). (O1)

no

To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures. (O1)

yes

To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO₂ and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase. (O3)

no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Although the next generation ESMs explicitly resolve a class of processes which are parameterized in contemporary ESMs, they still need to involve parameterizations of the processes operating at yet smaller scales below the resolved ones. Two sub-grid scale (SGS) process parameterizations that will still be needed in the foreseeable future, despite an increase in model resolution, are the turbulent mixing and cloud microphysics schemes. Therefore, it is top priority to improve these two parameterizations, especially since they are a major source of uncertainty in ESMs (Lang et al., 2023).

In the case of km-scale storm resolving models which are run on a global domain only a limited number of variables are possible to store as the output. For this reason, the internal parameters and variables relevant for SGS schemes operating within the model are typically unavailable for detailed analysis. Hence, the performance of SGS schemes needs to be assessed based on the state of the atmosphere which is influenced by their operation, using as proxies e.g. the thermodynamic structure of the boundary layer or the properties of clouds.

4.1 Sub-grid scale turbulence

4.1.1 Implemented SGS turbulence schemes

- Eddy-diffusivity mass-flux (EDMF) scheme (Angevine, 2005; Siebesma et al., 2007): used in IFS model. Designed to combine local (diffusivity) and non-local (mass-flux) contributions to mixing. Such an approach was inspired by how shallow cumulus convection operates and therefore, it is expected it represents best such a regime.
- Total turbulence energy (TTE) scheme (Mauritsen et al., 2007): used in some of the ICON runs of Cycle 2. It was developed for coarse grids applied in traditional climate models. The scheme is considered 'single-column' because there is no lateral mixing involved, i.e. only vertical mixing is considered. There are many similarity relationships deduced from experiments involved in the scheme.
- Smagorinsky scheme (Smagorinsky, 1963): used in most ICON runs. It was developed for the application in large eddy simulations (LES). Appreciated for its simplicity: in contrast to EDMF and TTE which have to be tuned whenever model resolution is changed, the Smagorinsky scheme does not require such tuning. On the other hand, although it works satisfactorily in LES type simulations, i.e. for resolutions O 100 m, the applicability to the current global model resolution (ca. 5 km by 5 km by 50 m) is debatable. Moreover, it involves Deardorff's stability correction (Deardorff, 1980; Stevens et al., 2000) which limits the mixing in the case of stable stratification. This aspect is crucially important for low-level clouds residing under temperature inversion separating moist boundary layer from the dry free troposphere, e.g. subtropical stratocumulus and shallow cumulus.

4.1.2 Observations from Cycle 2 simulations

Subtropical oceans The performance of SGS turbulence schemes in the trade-wind regime in Cycle 2 simulations was assessed by comparison with observations collected in the course

of the EUREC4A campaign in the northwestern Atlantic east of the island of Barbados (Stevens et al., 2021). The period from 22 Jan to 17 Feb 2020 was selected as reasonable overlap between observational and simulated periods. The analysis exploited radiosoundings and ground-based measurements performed at Barbados Cloud Observatory (Stevens et al., 2016; Christine Stephan et al., 2021). Fig. 1 shows the vertical profiles averaged over the selected period which were measured with radiosondes and simulated by the models at the grid point relevant for the location of the observatory.

Figure 1: Comparison of vertical structure of the boundary layer between radiosoundings launched at Barbados Cloud Observatory (black) and Cycle 2 simulations at the relevant grid point (red) for the period of 22 Jan 2020 - 17 Feb 2020, corresponding to EUREC4A campaign.

- In general, the simulations of Cycle 2 represent the main features of the trade-wind boundary layer vertical structure with its characteristic subcloud and cloud layers.
- The models give slightly lower temperature and lower specific humidity in the subcloud layer than measured which also results in lower virtual potential temperature.
- It was found that the influence of SGS scheme used in ICON (TTE vs Smagorinsky) is greater than that of the horizontal resolution (10 km vs 5 km). The simulation with TTE scheme exhibited significantly stronger winds at 10 meters, weaker surface sensible heat flux and stronger surface latent heat flux in relation to all other runs, despite a comparable sea surface temperature.
- The ICON model with either Smagorinsky or TTE scheme simulated drier cloud layer and

moister free troposphere with respect to the observations. Also, the use of Smagorinsky scheme resulted in very high relative humidity at the transition between subcloud and cloud layer which is typically coincident with the lifting condensation level (Lea Albright et al., 2022). Together, it signals the issue with the representation of vertical mixing in the conditions of stable stratification. IFS with its EDMF scheme and convection parameterizations captures the structure of the cloud layer much better which was expected as the scheme is well-suited for this boundary layer regime.

- The point above is consistent with the findings reported in deliverable D21 that ICON run with 10 km resolution using Smagorinsky scheme exhibits a radiation imbalance which was there attributed to too abundant low-level clouds.

Southern Ocean The quality of simulation of boundary layer clouds in the Southern Ocean is a long-standing problem in climate models (Trenberth and Fasullo, 2010; Kuma et al., 2020). It is affected by sub-grid scale parameterizations which can lead to biases in simulated cloud occurrence and properties. This type of clouds is very prevalent in the region and due to the size of the area and low sea surface albedo, errors can have a great impact on the Earth radiation budget.

The performance of SGS turbulence scheme in ICON was assessed by comparison with ship-based lidar and radiosonde observations. They provide a unique source of information about boundary layer clouds not available from satellites due to potential obscuration by higher-level clouds. We utilised observations from 24 RV *Polarstern* voyages, three RV *Tangaroa* voyages, one NB *Palmer* voyage, one HMNZS *Wellington* voyage, a set of 2015–2016 RSV *Aurora Australis* voyages, MARCUS voyages (McFarquhar et al., 2021) and the Macquarie Island station. A lidar simulator called the Automatic Lidar and Ceilometer Framework (ALCF) (Kuma et al., 2021) applied on the model data was used to provide a fair comparison between the model and observations. We further analysed co-located radiosonde observations to identify biases in some of the underlying cloud controlling factors (see sec. 4.1.3).

- Relative to lidar observations, boundary layer clouds in Cycle 2 ICON are generally underestimated by up to 50% depending on the voyage (Fig. 2). Although the measurement results suffer from a possible bias due to precipitation recognised as cloud, it is unlikely as large as the differences.
- Especially clouds below 2.5 km above sea level are substantially underestimated, and this is consistent across geographical regions in the Southern Ocean and seasons.

4.1.3 Observations from Cycle 3 simulations

Subtropical oceans In the analysis of Cycle 3 simulations we focused on subtropical stratocumulus and shallow cumulus clouds. They are important for the radiation balance of the planet due to their abundance and persistence. They not only determine the surface temperature in the present climate but also influence how the climate changes.

In addition to two core 5-year-long Cycle 3 simulations - IFS of resolution 4.4 km coupled with FESOM ocean model and ICON of resolution 5 km (ngc3028) - we analyzed a shorter 1-year-long ICON 5 km simulation (ngc3026) which used a modified Smagorinsky mixing scheme instead of the standard implementation used in the core simulation (ngc3028). The modification was designed to increase the vertical mixing in the conditions of strong static stability where

Figure 2: Observed (OBS) and ALCF-simulated (ICON) ground-based lidar cloud occurrence by height during 31 Southern Ocean voyages and the Macquarie Island station. ANT-*x* and PS*xxx* are voyages of RV *Polarstern*, TAN*xxxx* are voyages of RV *Tangaroa*, NBP1704 is a voyage of NB *Palmer* and AA15-16 are voyages of RSV *Aurora Australis*. Tracks in the free-running model were chosen to correspond to the ship tracks in the same geographical location and time of year.

the Deardoff's stability correction forces the effective eddy viscosity to vanish. It is particularly relevant for the trade-wind inversion above shallow cumulus and the capping inversion at stratocumulus top. Hence, the modification of the mixing scheme aimed at increasing the mixing between the boundary layer and the dry free troposphere, in this way preventing the accumulation of moisture in the boundary layer and reducing the amount of low clouds.

The representation of subtropical low clouds in the models and the effects of the SGS mixing schemes were closely investigated in several geographical regions of the size of 4x4 degrees selected based on cloud climatology: 4 regions of frequent stratocumulus cover and 4 regions of frequent shallow cumulus occurrence. They are marked on maps shown in Fig. 3 and 4. The stratocumulus regions are located in the northeastern Pacific, the northeastern Atlantic, the southeastern Pacific and the southeastern Atlantic; in the middle of 10x10 deg regions defined previously by Klein and Hartmann (1993). They are further referred to using the names of neighboring land areas: Californian, Canarian, Peruvian and Namibian, respectively. Those regions or their vicinity were intensively sampled during a number of measurement campaigns over past decades, e.g. DYCOMS, POST (Californian), ASTEX, ACE (Canarian), VOCALS (Peruvian), ORACLES (Namibian). The cumulus regions are located west and equator-ward from the stratocumulus ones, downwind following the trade winds: over the northern and the southern warm Pacific, in the northwestern and the southwestern Atlantic. Similarly, they are further referred to as Hawaiian, Galapagoan, Barbadian and Brazilian. The Barbadian was targeted by the recent EUREC4A measurement campaign (Stevens et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Mean TOA albedo in the three model runs of Cycle 3 and satellite observations (CERES-EBAF 2000-2021 climatology) with overlaid 4x4 deg boxes denoting selected regions of frequent stratocumulus (black) and shallow cumulus (red) occurrence. The stratocumulus regions are in the middle of those previously defined by Klein and Hartmann (1993) which are marked with dashed black boxes for reference.

SGS parameterizations influence the dependence of cloud properties on environmental conditions. Whether the models correctly represent the relationship between cloud properties and their thermodynamic environment was studied with the use of basic parameters available in model output. Klein and Hartmann (1993) found a universal linear dependence of stratiform cloudiness on lower tropospheric stability (LTS) which is the difference of potential temperature

Figure 4: Mean liquid water path in the three model runs of Cycle 3 with selected regions of frequent stratocumulus (black) and shallow cumulus (red) occurrence as in Fig. 3

between the level of 700 hPa (typically located in the free troposphere) and the surface. Instead of cloud fraction, which is not a well defined quantity in km-scale models, we employed liquid water path (LWP) as the proxy for cloud amount and investigated its correlation with LTS.

- In general, both core Cycle 3 simulations (IFS 4.4 km and ICON 5 km with standard Smagorinsky scheme) correctly represent the geographical pattern of stratocumulus cloudiness over subtropical eastern oceans as indicated by TOA albedo (Fig. 3) and LWP (Fig. 4). On the other hand, the amount of shallow cumulus in both simulations is likely overestimated over subtropical eastern Atlantic and warm Pacific which is suggested by the albedo being significantly higher than satellite observations.
- The annual cycle of albedo is well captured by the ICON with the standard Smagorinsky scheme (Fig. 5) in 4 stratocumulus regions and by the IFS in the Canarian and Peruvian regions. However, the models do not perform equally well in cumulus regions.
- Despite comparable geographical patterns of mean LWP, the ICON model gives LWP more than 2 times higher than the IFS in all regions of interest (see the different ranges of LWP in the panels of Fig. 6). Presumably, the Smagorinsky scheme allows too little mixing through the inversion and in consequence traps too much liquid water in the low-level marine clouds.
- Both core simulations correctly represent the linear increase of LWP with LTS (Fig. 6). The range of LTS is realistic considering reanalysis (Klein and Hartmann, 1993).
- The modification of the Smagorinsky scheme led to a number of consequences. In comparison with the ICON simulation using the standard scheme, albedo was significantly decreased in 3 stratocumulus regions (except for canarian) but remained nearly the same in 4 cumulus regions (compare Fig. 3 and 5). Similarly, LWP decreased in 4 stratocumulus regions, becoming comparable to the IFS, but remained unchanged in 4 cumulus regions. Importantly, the linear relationship between LWP and LTS does not exist any more.

Figure 5: Annual cycle of TOA albedo in the selected regions: comparison of monthly means between the three model runs of Cycle 3 and satellite observations (CERES-EBAF 2000-2021 climatology).

Figure 6: Correlation between monthly means of liquid water path and lower tropospheric stability in the selected regions for the three model runs of Cycle 3.

Handling stratocumulus and shallow cumulus cloud with their respective boundary layer structures remains challenging with one single SGS parametrization even at kilometer-scale resolution. This highlights the importance of careful physically-informed design of parameterization schemes. Otherwise, simple tuning aimed at improving the representation of one regime might worsen the representation of the other. This was shown here on the example of subtropical stratocumulus and cumulus regimes.

Southern Ocean The results of Cycle 3 ICON simulation performed with the use of standard Smagorinsky scheme was assessed against radiosonde observations over the Southern Ocean. The radiosonde profiles were compared with simulated thermodynamic profiles co-located with radiosonde launches, analogously to cloud observations presented in sec. 4.1.2. Here, we analysed radiosonde data from the TAN1802 voyage (Kremser et al., 2021) of RV *Tangaroa* (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Composition of **(a)** observed (voyage TAN1802) and **(b)** model (Cycle 3 ICON with standard Smagorinsky) profiles of potential temperature. Shown is also sea surface temperature (SST) and the lifting condensation level (LCL) histogram and median.

- The ICON simulation displays a deeper mixed-layer depth, higher median lifting condensation level, higher potential temperature at 5 km above sea level, and much smaller variability of the potential temperature profile than observations.
- In observations, the profiles are more conducive of inducing fog or near-surface cloud due to more stable situations confining mixing near the surface, and low lifting condensation level inducing condensation of water vapour in any rising parcels close to the surface. To determine if these differences could be the main source of the cloud biases remains to be investigated.

4.2 Cloud microphysics

Both IFS and ICON parameterize cloud microphysics using single-moment bulk schemes, which are the simplest models available (Grabowski et al., 2019). The resolved variables in these models are the specific mass of condensate in different categories, e.g. cloud water, rain, ice or graupel. Such an approach requires that the rates of transfer of mass between different categories are defined. These rates cannot be calculated from first principles, but are estimated empirically, for example from idealized fine-resolution cloud simulations. Additional assumptions need to be made about the shape of the hydrometeor size distribution, hydrometeor sedimentation velocity and about concentration of aerosols. The large number of arbitrary parameters increases uncertainty in microphysics modeling (Morrison et al., 2020). Moreover, comparison of microphysics models in idealized cases reveals that single-moment bulk schemes can significantly deviate from more detailed models (Hill et al., 2023).

The paper of Lang et al. (2023) is a clear illustration of uncertainty associated with using single-moment bulk schemes in ESMs. The authors compared ICON simulations with single-moment bulk microphysics to ICON simulations with double-moment bulk microphysics. In addition to mass fraction, the double-moment scheme considers also the number concentration for each category of hydrometeors. The study shows significant differences in humidity in shallow clouds

between the two simulation runs.

NextGEMS cycle 3 simulations can also be used to assess errors associated with single-moment microphysics. We compare ICON and IFS runs that both use single-moment bulk microphysics, but of different kind. Differences in the conversion rates assumed in both models can affect the relative amounts of different types of condensate. Figure 8 shows how frozen water is divided into categories in IFS and in ICON. ICON has three categories: snow, ice and graupel, while IFS has only two: snow and ice. Both models predict similar snow fraction of around 65%. In IFS the remaining 35% is ice, while in ICON ice fraction is only around 15% and graupel fraction is around 20%. Graupel sediments much faster than ice. Therefore categorizing 20% of frozen water as graupel in ICON, as opposed to ice in IFS, can cause significant differences in lifetime of clouds. It is a direct result of differences in the single-moment bulk microphysics used by both models. This illustrates the need for a more realistic microphysics model, preferably one without arbitrary categorization of hydrometeors.

Figure 8: Fraction of global water solid content in different categories. Results of the Cycle 3 simulations: ICON 5 km and IFS 4.4 km coupled with FESOM.

4.3 Improving SGS parameterizations

We started exploration of more realistic SGS parameterizations that could potentially be used in ESMs. This will be our focus in phase two of the project.

The Smagorinsky model assumes that the local energy production and the energy dissipation at small scales are at equilibrium. The equilibrium assumption is also employed in the TTE scheme to model the local dissipation rate. However, a number of recent research works addresses the problem of non-equilibrium turbulence where rapid changes of forcing cause deviations from the classical Kolmogorov scaling. A universal, although non-classical relation between the turbulence dissipation rate, turbulence kinetic energy and turbulence length scale was proposed by [Vassilicos \(2015\)](#). This non-equilibrium scaling relation was observed in numerous laboratory experiments. In our recent contribution ([Wacławczyk et al., 2022](#)) we analyzed data from the startocumulus-topped boundary layer and detected, for the first time, the non-equilibrium dissipation scaling in the atmospheric turbulence. Taking into account the non-equilibrium effects in the SGS model will improve existing parametrization schemes.

Another method we are interested in is fractal reconstruction of SGS variables ([Akinlabi et al., 2019](#)). Turbulence is self-similar, i.e. has similar characteristics at different length scales. Therefore based on the fractal structure of resolved variables, and knowing the expected amount of turbulent kinetic energy in the sub-grid scales, it is possible to reconstruct variables at scales smaller than resolved.

Regarding modeling of cloud microphysics, we are considering using the method of super-droplets ([Shima et al., 2009](#)). In this method Lagrangian particle-like objects are used to represent hydrometeors. This type of microphysics modeling has been gaining popularity over the last decade in detailed, large-eddy simulations (LES) of clouds. However, its applicability to ESMs has not yet been explored. One potential obstacle is stochasticity inherent to the method. We are exploring ways of decreasing the amount of stochasticity.

Our strategy is to test these parameterizations in the University of Warsaw Lagrangian Cloud Model (UWLCM) ([Dziekan et al., 2019](#)), a LES model developed by us. It is much quicker to implement, run and analyze parameterizations in LES than in global models. Moreover, ESM resolution is getting closer and closer to a coarse-scale LES, making LES a convenient testbed for parameterizations.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

There were difficulties with finding competent candidates for post-doc positions. These positions were filled with a substantial delay, in July and October 2022.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

Close collaboration with T6.3 Validation and development of the planetary boundary layer, because SGS turbulence model influences and manifests in the structure of the boundary layer through regulating vertical mixing.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>